

INNOVATIVE BULGE TEST SETUP TO CHARACTERIZE THIN BEAM VACUUM WINDOWS *

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Abstract

As part of the International Muon Collider study, a thin beam vacuum window is being developed at CERN. This window is required for the final cooling, where the charged particles travel from the vacuum chamber to the absorber; here, the beam loses momentum to cross a second window entering in a RF cavity that increases the longitudinal momentum. The best absorber for the final cooling is hydrogen. As the absorber should be installed inside a high field focusing solenoid, the hydrogen density should be as high as possible, ideally liquid or high pressure gas, to have a reasonable solenoid length. To evaluate the performance of the window, it is necessary to study the tightness at cryogenic temperatures, resistance to burst, high temperature and beam-induced damage. The main objective of the proposed work is to design and validate a versatile bulge test setup for the mechanical characterization of thin windows at different pressures and temperatures to cover all operating conditions, from 77 K to 293 K and ideally above. Due to the low thicknesses, a non-contact measuring technique based on a confocal chromatic sensor is proposed.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical properties of thin films, with typical thicknesses in the range of microns or less, cannot be extrapolated indiscriminately from bulk materials due to differences in geometry and related effects. In thin films, the geometrical and microstructural dimensions are of the same order of magnitude. The main effects are the difference in grain structure, dislocation density, and vacancy concentration. Accurate characterization of the mechanics of thin films requires the use of appropriate experimental methods.

In 1959, Beams et al. [1] introduced bulge testing as a technique to determine the mechanical properties of free-standing membranes fixed along the edges and uniformly pressurized from one side. The objective of the bulge tests is to evaluate the stress-strain behavior of the membrane by measuring its maximum deflection as a function of the applied pressure. The development of analytical models for the pressure-displacement relationship of circular [2, 3], square [4, 5], and rectangular [4, 6] membranes, together with the introduction of the micromachining technology in the semiconductor industry [7, 8], made it possible to improve the accuracy of bulge test measurements significantly. Most bulge test setups are designed to study the mechanical properties of thin films at room temperature [9–13].

This work aims to extend the application of bulge testing to the characterization of various shapes of membranes

over a wide range of temperatures. The primary application is the design of a beam window for the final cooling stage of the Muon Collider. A simple and versatile setup was developed and validated at CERN for tests at 77 K, 293 K and up to around 500 K. Previous design and optimization of the system were possible by Finite Element (FE) analyses. Experimental results of LPCVD Si₃N₄ membranes are presented.

DESIGN OF THE SETUP

Mechanical Components

The mechanical assembly was designed and developed to be simple, compact and versatile to be used for all temperature configurations. A schematic representation of the components of the system is reported in Fig. 1a, while a picture of the real assembly is shown in Fig. 1b.

A copper or invar-copper flange (7) is designed to accommodate the sample in a special slot created on the top surface. The flange is screwed on a cylindrical copper support (8). A pressure cell (9) is drilled on the top of the cylinder into which helium (He) gas is injected to apply uniform pressure to the membrane. A small steel enclosure is created via flanges. In particular, a bottom steel flange (5) is screwed around the copper cylinder; it has a vacuum inlet (4) and a feedthrough connector (3). A top steel flange (1) allows the connection to a smaller flange with an integrated sapphire viewport (2). The viewport allows the light from the optical sensor to be projected on the membrane. The enclosure has a dual role: a) thermally isolate the flange with the membrane from the outside temperature to maintain the desired temperature conditions during testing by creating the vacuum, and b) protect the optical sensor from damage in case of membrane breakage thanks to the glass viewport that separates the sensor from the rest of the setup. The leak tightness of the vacuum chamber and pressure cell are ensured by Viton O-ring or flat gaskets (6).

Sample Mounting

A typical sample consists of a freestanding membrane supported by a silicon frame. The sample is bonded to a special slot created on the dedicated flange, as schematically shown in Fig. 2, allowing good repeatability of sample placement. The sample is oriented such that when it is pressurized, a compressive state develops at the interface between the frame and the membrane, preventing delamination phenomena and undesired failure of the membrane.

The substrate can be either copper or invar. Copper is selected to enhance the thermal efficiency of the setup owing to its high thermal conductivity. Additionally, as a soft material, it mitigates the transmission of excessive forces to

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Figure 1: Mechanical assembly: (a) scheme of the system with components, and (b) picture of the real system.

Figure 2: Schematic cross-section of the flange-pressure cell-sample system after sample mounting by bonding.

the membrane when the flange is secured to the copper cylinder. However, the FE analysis showed that a compressive or tensile stress state develops in the membrane during cooling or heating, respectively. This is due to the mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients between copper and silicon. An invar substrate allows the membrane to maintain an almost zero stress state with temperature variation, but it does affect the thermal efficiency of the system, as shown in Fig. 3. An invar-copper flange represents the best compromise between mechanical and thermal performance. A picture of the invar-copper flange is shown in Fig. 4. An invar disk with a thickness of 2 mm is brazed to the copper flange with a radial gap of 100 μm to accommodate different thermal deformations.

Instrumentation

A non-contact optical sensor based on confocal chromatic light is used to measure membrane deflection during bulge tests. A servomotor stage moves the optical sensor horizontally, allowing it to be positioned correctly in the center of the membrane. Vertical positioning is accomplished with a manual system of micrometer screws. The temperatures of the membrane, which is assumed to be the same as that of the flange on which it is bonded, and other system components are measured by PT100s. A pressure control system with

Figure 3: FEM temperature distribution after cooling from 293 K to 77 K on flanges of different materials: (a) copper, (b) invar, (c) invar-copper.

Figure 4: Invar-copper flange designed to house the sample for low and high temperature measurements.

an integrated feedback loop controls the pressure applied to the membrane during testing. A gas injection and release control system allows cyclic loading.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the three temperature configurations of the setup at: (a) 77 K, (b) 293 K, and (c) above 500 K.

Three Temperature Configurations

Three temperature configurations of the bulge test setup were developed for measurements at 77 K, 293 K and up to around 500 K. Figure 5a shows the setup operating at cryogenic temperatures. The membrane is cooled to 77 K by conduction by immersing the copper cylinder into a liquid Nitrogen (N_2) Dewar. An anti-condensation system based on gaseous N_2 is installed on the top flange. Figure 5b illustrates the configuration of the system at 293 K. In this case, the mechanical assembly is instrumented only with the optical sensor and pressure control system, because there is no need for temperature control. Figure 5c shows the setup used for high-temperature measurements. A heating band ($P=480$ W) surrounds and heats the copper cylinder potentially above 500 K. A PID controller regulates and measures the temperature of the copper cylinder. The membrane is then heated to the desired temperature by conduction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The bulge test setup was experimentally validated by testing freestanding Silicon Nitride (Si_3N_4) square membranes with dimensions of $6\text{ mm} \times 6\text{ mm}$ and a thickness of 1000 nm, surrounded by a silicon frame of $10\text{ mm} \times 10\text{ mm}$ and $200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thick. The samples were pressurized at a constant rate of 10 mbar/s until failure. Figure 6 shows the results of bulge tests at three different temperatures: 77 K, 293 K, and 415 K. The graph shows the evolution of the pressure difference on the membrane as a function of its maximum deflection. The results show that the temperature affects the mechanical response of the material. In particular, the higher the temperature, the lower the elastic stiffness of the membrane. In addition, different pressure values at failure were measured in the three cases. It turns out that the membrane fails at a pressure of about 6.5 bar at both low and room temperature; at high temperature, the value of the pressure at failure is 4.9 bar. It is worth specifying that these curves are preliminary results aimed at demonstrating

the functioning of the setup. Further investigation of different shapes of Si_3N_4 membranes will be discussed in future works.

Figure 6: Evolution of the pressure applied to the membrane as a function of its maximum deflection during bulge tests at three different temperatures: 77 K, 293 K, and 415 K.

CONCLUSION

A setup for bulge tests of thin membranes at 77 K, 293 K and up to around 500 K was designed, developed and validated at CERN. The bulge test setup allows the determination of the elastic properties of the membranes and is also designed to perform fracture toughness, creep and fatigue tests. The application of the system for the characterization of a beam window in the final cooling stage of the Muon Collider was presented.

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